

“Development of Zeolite-Incorporated PEBA-PEMA Blend Mixed Matrix Membranes for the Enhancement of n-Butanol Recovery through Pervaporation”

Praveenkumar Denganavar, Jayachandra Krishnegowda and Santosh Choudhari*

School of Basic and Applied Sciences, Dayanand Sagar University, Kudlu gate campus-560068, India

Abstract

Biobutanol is considered as one of the promising next-generation biofuels compared to traditional bioethanol due to its higher energy content, lower volatility and greater compatibility. However, because of its product inhibition, low yields and expensive separation process makes it difficult to produce biobutanol on a wide scale through the fermentation process. Pervaporation (PV) emerged as a promising membrane-based technology which separates biobutanol with excellent selectivity, low energy consumption and operational scalability. Considering this background, primarily we have developed PEBA-PEMA blend membranes. Furthermore, we have incorporated the ZSM-5 zeolite in to PEBA-PEMA blend membranes to enhance the hydrophobicity for pervaporation performance of the membranes, which separates biobutanol in more efficient manner. The developed mixed matrix membranes were characterized through ATR-IR, SEM, XRD and contact angle measurement. The blend mixed matrix membrane PBPM5-5 containing 5 wt% of ZSM-5 zeolite exhibited the highest pervaporation performance yielding a flux of $0.21 \text{ kgm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$ and a separation factor of 21.3, which is an 80% enhancement in flux and approximately a 3-fold increase in the separation factor as compared to the pure PEBA. Therefore, this work examines the combined effects of polymer blending and zeolite incorporation for butanol separations using binary solutions with more efficacy compared to pure PEBA.

Keywords: Biofuel; Butanol; Pervaporation; Polyether block amide; ZSM-5 zeolite

*Corresponding author

Dr. Santosh Choudhari

1. Introduction

The volatility of crude oil prices continues to challenge global energy security, particularly in developing countries dependent on petroleum imports. The rise in crude oil prices is directly affecting the finances of the growing countries due to hikes in petrol and diesel prices. This increase will eventually impact the markets that are directly and indirectly dependent on the fuel. Biofuels, particularly butanol, can be blended with gasoline, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and support rural economies. Also it offers superior fuel properties, including higher energy content, lower volatility, and better gasoline compatibility[1]. Furthermore, it yields a positive impact on the nation's energy requirement, benefits the environment with greenhouse sustainability, and encourages development of rural and suburban areas.

Bio-butanol, a promising biofuel, is produced via acetone-butanol-ethanol (ABE) fermentation from substrates like sugarcane bagasse, molasses, and food waste. However, its production is limited by toxicity to microorganisms, leading to low yields and expensive purification steps[2]. To overcome these challenges, in situ separation methods have been explored, such as liquid-liquid extraction, gas stripping, freeze crystallization, perstraction, membrane distillation, adsorption, and pervaporation (PV)[3–8]. Among various separation techniques, pervaporation stands out as a membrane-based technology that is highly energy-efficient, environmentally friendly, and cost-effective. It offers low initial operating expenses and does not negatively affect microorganisms, making it particularly attractive for applications in bioprocessing and environmentally sensitive operations[9-10].

In the PV process, the development of membranes with high permeation flux, excellent separation selectivity and mechanical stability is critical to achieving efficient and sustainable separation performance. In recent decades, several polymeric materials are used to develop membranes and applied to separate acetone-butanol-ethanol (ABE) components from aqueous solutions and one them is PEBA 2533[11]. It is a widely used commercial copolymer made from polyether and block amide, known for its excellent chemical, mechanical, and thermal stability[12–16]. Comprising 80% polyether (soft segments) and 20% polyamide (hard segments), it is processed via simple solution casting without any cross linkers[17]. PEBA membranes show strong affinity for butanol and offer higher butanol flux than benchmark PDMS membranes in PV process[18,19]. However, their performance is still inadequate for large-scale use. The development of polymeric blend membranes is one of the most effective approaches for improving separation performance[11]. It is a highly effective technique that combines the synergistic properties of different polymers into a unique composite material, overcoming the deficiencies of the individual polymers, and achieves the necessary performance characteristics. Furthermore,

polymer blends provide several benefits due to their uniformity, brevity, and cost-effectiveness. In view of this, we selected PEMA to blend with PEBA, using Hansen's solubility parameter approach. The Hansen's solubility parameters offer an effective method for evaluating the affinity between polymeric membrane materials and organic solvents, rendering them a valuable resource for identifying appropriate pervaporation membrane materials [20]. Several earlier investigations demonstrated that HSPs has a great ability for choosing materials for pervaporation membranes [21–23]. Table 1 illustrates Hansen's solubility parameters for polymers, butanol, and water, from which the total cohesion (δ_t) is computed using equation 1. It is evident from the table that PEMA has a strong affinity for butanol, as δ_t values of PEMA are much closer to butanol than water. Expectedly, blending improved separation performance of the PEBA however, blend compatibility restricted the loading level. To address this, hydrophobic zeolite ZSM-5 was incorporated to further enhance flux and selectivity.

$$\delta_t = \sqrt{\delta_d^2 + \delta_p^2 + \delta_h^2} \quad (1)$$

	δ_d	δ_p	δ_h	δ_t	Δ - Distance parameter
Water	15.5	16	42.3	47.80	$\Delta_{\text{PEBA-Butanol}} = 9.34$
Butanol	16	5.7	15.8	23.20	$\Delta_{\text{PEBA-Water}} = 36.64$
PEBA	17.6	7.6	6.8	20.34	$\Delta_{\text{PEMA-Butanol}} = 9.95$
PEMA	18.64	10.52	7.51	22.68	$\Delta_{\text{PEMA-Water}} = 35.46$

Table 1. Hansen's solubility parameters and calculated distance parameters.

The incorporation of fillers into polymeric membranes, producing mixed matrix membranes (MMMs), is considered a promising way to improve their separation performance. Zeolite, such as ZSM-5, has improved the pervaporation performance of pure polymeric membrane materials for the separation of organic compounds from aqueous solutions due to its high surface area, hydrophobicity, and uniform pore size distribution [24,25]. Several studies have demonstrated that incorporating zeolite into polymeric materials significantly improves their separation performance [26,27].

Therefore, this work examines the combined effects of polymer blending and ZSM-5 incorporation on butanol separation, supported by structural characterization and systematic performance evaluation.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

PEBAX-2533 polymer was procured from Arkema (France). Polyethyl methacrylate polymer was procured from Sigma-Aldrich, India. ZSM-5 zeolite powder purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific India Pvt. limited. n-butanol and acetone were purchased from S D Fine- Chemicals limited, Mumbai, India. Ethanol was purchased from Hayman group limited, Eastways Park, Witham, UK. All chemicals are of analytical grade. Double distilled water was used throughout the research.

2.2. Membrane preparation

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the fabrication of mixed matrix membranes.

In order to prepare pure blend membranes, required amount of PEBA and PEMA were added to 100 ml of butanol to make 5 wt% (wt/vol) solution. The mixture was stirred at 80°C for 24 hours to ensure complete solubility of the polymers. The resulting solution was then cooled to room temperature, and required amount of homogeneous solution was evenly dispensed into a clean glass petri dish. The dishes were subsequently maintained at ambient temperature for 48 hours in dust-free environment to allow the evaporation of solvent. The membranes were subsequently removed and dried in a hot air oven at 50°C for 24 hours to remove any residual solvent. The membranes were named as PBPM0 to PBPM10, the latter number indicates the wt% of PEMA blended with PEBA. To prepare mixed matrix membrane, required amount of ZSM-5 zeolite was weighed and then dispersed in butanol. The mixture was vigorously stirred for 24 hours and further sonicated for 2 hours to break any agglomerates present. Afterwards, 5 g mixture (95:5) of PEBA and PEMA polymers was added to the above zeolite-butanol suspension under continuous stirring and heated at 80°C for 24 hours. The remaining procedure is same as that of the pure blend membranes. The preparation scheme of the mixed matrix membranes is shown in Figure 1. The membranes were designated as PBPM5-0 to PBPM5-8, the first number representing the amount wt% of PEMA in the blend and the latter number indicating the amount of ZSM-5 zeolite incorporated. The membrane thickness was evaluated using a dial thickness gauge (G-2, Misumi, Japan) and observed to be around $80 \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$.

2.3. Structural, Morphological, and Surface Characterization of Membranes

The water contact angle of the PV membranes was evaluated using a sessile drop contact angle (CA) analyser (Dura-vision Systems India). Attenuated total reflectance infrared spectroscopy (ATR-IR) (Perkin Elmer spectrum GX, Series 59387, UK) was employed to elucidate the functional groups present within the membranes, operating within a range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 2 cm^{-1} . Morphological characterization of the membranes was conducted using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV (Carl Zeiss EVO-18, Germany). Prior to imaging, all samples intended for SEM analysis underwent vacuum drying for 24 hours and were subsequently coated with gold using the sputter-coating technique. An X-ray diffractometer (Bruker D8 advance, Germany) was used to assess the crystal structure of ZSM-5 zeolite and mixed matrix membranes within the range of 5-90° with an increment of 0.02 at room temperature.

2.4. Swelling studies

Swelling studies of the mixed matrix membranes were conducted using a 20 g/L aqueous butanol solution. Initially, membranes were dried at 50°C for 24 hours in an electronically controlled oven (Servewell Instruments Pvt. Ltd., India), then cooled to room temperature and weighed to record their dry mass. Subsequently, the membranes were immersed in sealed jars containing the 20g/L butanol aqueous solution and equilibrated at 40°C for 24 hours. After equilibration, membranes were carefully removed, blotted with filter paper to eliminate excess surface liquid, and immediately weighed using a high-precision digital microbalance (BSA224S-CW, Sartorius, India). Each measurement was performed in triplicate, and average values were

reported to ensure reproducibility. The percentage degree of swelling (DS) was computed using the formula shown below.

$$\text{Degree of swelling (DS \%)} = \frac{W_s - W_d}{W_d} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

W_s and W_d denote the weights of the swollen membrane and the dried membrane, respectively.

2.5. Pervaporation experiment

Pervaporation experiments were conducted using a custom-designed PV setup. The fabricated membrane was installed in a stainless-steel PV cell with an effective mass transfer area of 19.6cm². The feed solution was continuously circulated over the membrane surface at a flow rate of 15 L/h using a circulation pump, while a vacuum pump maintained the downstream pressure at 5 torr. Permeate liquid vapors were condensed in liquid nitrogen traps and collected. Prior to data collection, the system was stabilized under operating conditions for about 1 hour, followed by a 2-hour steady-state pervaporation performance. The flux was calculated by weighing the permeate sample. The feed and permeate samples were analysed using a gas chromatography instrument [GC2024, Shimadzu, Japan].

The following formulas (2-4) were used to compute the permeation flux (J), separation factor (β), and pervaporation separation index (PSI) from the experimental data.

$$J = \frac{W}{At} \quad (3)$$

$$\beta = \frac{P_o/P_w}{F_o/F_w} \quad (4)$$

$$PSI = J(\beta - 1) \quad (5)$$

Where W denotes the weight of permeate (kg), A signifies the active membrane area (m²) in contact with feed, and t represents the PV experiment time duration (h). P_o , P_w , F_o , and F_w represent the mass fractions of organic compounds and water on the permeate and feed sides, respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Effect of PEMA blending with PEBA on PV performance

Figure 2. Effect of wt% of PEMA blending with PEBA on flux and separation factor.

In order to see the effect of PEMA blending with PEBA on the PV performance, blend membranes were implemented to separate butanol from 20g/L aqueous butanol solutions at 40°C. From the Figure 2 it can be clearly seen that both flux and separation factor improved with the PEMA blending. The upward trend observed up to 5 wt% and then there is slight decline in the performance. This might be due to blend incompatibility arising at a higher blend composition. However, membrane PBPM5 containing 5 wt% of PEMA, demonstrated the flux of 0.19 kgm⁻²h⁻¹ with a separation factor of 15.5, which is almost 50% enhancement in flux and twice the separation factor obtained for pure PEBA membrane. As the blend compatibility puts restriction on PEMA blending and in order to enhance the separation performance further, we incorporated ZSM-5 zeolite in the blend membrane. The 5 wt% PEMA blend composition was selected for zeolite modification as it has given highest PV separation performance. The influence of the different wt% of ZSM-5 zeolite loading on physical

properties of PBPM5 membranes and also towards the recovery of butanol from the 20 g/L butanol-aqueous solution at 40°C was investigated.

3.2. Effect of zeolite addition on physical properties and PV performance on PBPM5 blend membrane

3.2.1. Scanning electron microscopy

Figure 3. SEM images of mixed matrix membrane with different weight percentage of ZSM-5 zeolite a) 0wt%, b) 1 wt%, c) 3wt%, d) 5wt%, e) 8wt%.

SEM analysis revealed clear morphological differences between the PBPM5 blend membrane and ZSM-5-loaded mixed matrix membranes as shown in Figure 3. The neat blend membrane exhibited a smooth, homogeneous surface, whereas increasing ZSM-5 content (0–8 wt%) resulted in progressively rougher and lumpier morphologies, particularly beyond 5 wt%, indicating reduced interfacial compatibility. Despite this, the mixed matrix membranes remained continuous and uniform, with an average thickness of ~80 μm, and no visible pinholes or cracks. The ZSM-5 zeolite particles appeared well-dispersed and firmly embedded within the polymer matrix, with no detectable interfacial voids, suggesting strong inorganic–organic adhesion that could enhance molecular interactions and separation performance.

3.2.2. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy

Figure 4.(a) ATR-IR spectra, (b) XRD patterns of pure ZSM-5 zeolite, and mixed matrix membranes with different wt% of ZSM-5 zeolite.

The chemical structures and compositions of membranes containing varying concentrations of ZSM-5 zeolite were systematically characterized using attenuated total reflectance infrared (ATR-IR) spectroscopy, as presented in Figure 4a. The ATR-IR spectrum of pure ZSM-5 zeolite showed typical framework vibrational bands, such as a strong asymmetric Si–O–Si stretching vibration centered about $\sim 1100\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which is a sign of the silicate network[28]. The double five-membered ring vibrations were represented by a prominent band at approximately 550 cm^{-1} , which functioned as a fingerprint of the MFI-type structure. In the presence of surface silanol groups and adsorbed moisture, broad absorption bands were found at approximately 3440 cm^{-1} and 1635 cm^{-1} . These bands were attributed to the stretching vibrations of the oxygen–hydrogen bond and the bending vibrations, respectively.

PBPM5-0 represents a pure PEBA-PEMA blend, which exhibits characteristic peaks of both PEBA and PEMA. Amide functional groups were characterized by N–H stretching at 3296 cm^{-1} , C=O stretching at 1740 cm^{-1} , and N–H bending at 1640 cm^{-1} . The symmetric and asymmetric C–H stretching vibrations of methylene groups were observed at 2926 cm^{-1} and 2847 cm^{-1} , respectively. A strong absorption band at 1105 cm^{-1} was assigned to the C–O–C ether linkages present in the polymer backbone. The presence of PEMA was further confirmed by the C–O stretching at 1203 cm^{-1} and a secondary ester C=O stretching band near 1640 cm^{-1} , which overlapped with the amide bending vibration. A peak at 1097 cm^{-1} further confirmed ether linkages due to C–O–C bonds[29,30]. From PBPM5-0 to PBPM5-8 the intensity of the peak at 1100 cm^{-1} and 3440 cm^{-1} representing the characteristic peak of Si–O–Si linkage and silanol groups, gradually increased. This is due to an increase in the ZSM-5 content in the membrane.

The ATR-IR spectra of the ZSM-5 zeolite, and PBPM5 mixed-matrix membranes exhibited characteristics that indicate the presence of both zeolite and polymers. Notably, there were no new peaks or significant shifts in the existing bands. This observation implies that no covalent bonds or chemical reactions are taking place between the zeolite and polymer phases. Nevertheless, the well-defined and integrated spectral features suggest strong physical interactions and effective dispersion of the ZSM-5 zeolite within the polymer matrix.

3.2.3. X-Ray diffraction

The crystalline structure of pure ZSM-5 zeolite, and PBPM5-0 to PBPM5-8 mixed matrix membranes was characterized using X-ray diffraction, as illustrated in Figure 4b. The XRD patterns reveal distinct characteristic diffraction peaks of ZSM-5 zeolite in the 2θ ranges of $7\text{--}9^\circ$ and $23\text{--}25^\circ$, corresponding to its well-known crystalline structure, which is similar to already reported results[26,31]. In contrast, the XRD pattern of the PEBA-PEMA blend membrane exhibits a broad diffraction halo, centered between $16\text{--}25^\circ$, indicative of the amorphous nature of the PEBA-PEMA polymer matrix. Incorporation of 1–8 wt% ZSM-5 zeolite into the PEBA-PEMA blend to form mixed matrix membranes results in XRD patterns exhibiting a superimposition of ZSM-5 zeolite crystalline peaks and the broad amorphous halo of the polymer blend. The emergence of sharp peaks in the $7\text{--}9^\circ$ and $23\text{--}25^\circ$ range confirms the presence of crystalline ZSM-5 zeolite. With increasing zeolite loading (1–8 wt%), the intensity of these peaks increases, indicating enhanced ZSM-5 zeolite dispersion and successful integration within the polymer matrix[32].

3.2.4. Effect of ZSM-5 zeolite addition on PV

Figure 5. Effect of ZSM-5 zeolite on (a) flux and separation factor. (b) % degree of swelling and contact angle. (c) PSI, and Effect of temperature on (d) flux and separation factor, (e) water and butanol fluxes. (f) Variation of $\ln J_w$ and $\ln J_b$.

The influence of the different wt% of ZSM-5 zeolite loading on PBPM5 blend membranes towards the recovery of butanol from the 20 g/L butanol-aqueous solution at 40°C was investigated and obtained results are shown in Figure 5a. The figure clearly shows the incorporation of ZSM-5 zeolite increased, both the separation factor and flux gradually; both the factors simultaneously increased up to 5 wt% and then decreased at 8 wt%. The increase in flux and separation factor values with the addition of ZSM-5 zeolite are due to increase in membrane hydrophobicity and membrane swelling. The membrane hydrophobicity was analyzed through measuring contact angle and swelling studies were conducted to measure swelling percentage; the obtained values shown in Figure 5b. PBPM5-0 membrane showed water contact angle of 58° which steadily increased with the incorporation of ZSM-5 zeolite, and the mixed matrix membrane showed a contact angle of 77° for 8 wt% of ZSM-5 zeolite. Similarly, the inclusion of ZSM-5 zeolite also caused an increase in membrane swelling, which went from 2.1% for PBPM5-0 membrane to 4% for 5 wt% zeolite loaded membrane.

The water contact angle results show an increase in contact angle with addition of zeolite. It means that the surface of the membranes becomes more hydrophobic with the zeolite addition and results in more selective sorption of the PEBA molecules relative to water molecules which in turn increased the separation factor. This is evident as the ZSM-5 zeolite particles have a hydrophobic nature [28]. Similarly, increase in membrane swelling lead to faster diffusion of molecules leading to enhanced flux. Generally, a trade-off relationship is observed between flux and separation factor [33]. Interestingly, in the current study, the developed mixed matrix membranes anti trade-off relationship. This behaviour may be linked to increased hydrophobic characteristics and sufficient swelling of the membranes.

The pervaporation separation index is a tool to find the membrane that shows the fine balance between the separation factor and flux. The PSI values were computed using equation 5, and the results are presented in Figure 5c. Observations indicate that the PSI values increase with the increase in zeolite content in the membrane, peaking at 5 wt%, followed by a decline at 8 wt%. The observed rise in PSI values can be linked to a simultaneous increase in both flux and separation factor values. The membrane PBPM5-5 exhibited the highest PSI value of 4.8, whereas the membrane containing PBPM5-8 demonstrated the lowest PSI value of 2.9. Consequently, the PBPM5-5 membrane containing 5 wt% of ZSM-5 zeolite was selected for subsequent studies.

3.2.5. Effect of temperature

To assess the influence of operating temperature on pervaporation performance of the membranes, experiments were conducted using a 20 g/L aqueous butanol solution across a temperature range of 30 to 60°C. Figure 5d

displays the resulting total flux and separation factor data. The results reveal a positive correlation between membrane performance and feed temperature. For a more thorough evaluation, the individual fluxes of butanol and water were computed and plotted versus temperature, as illustrated in Figure 5e. This analysis indicates that the observed increase in overall flux is due to concurrent increase in both butanol and water permeation fluxes as indicated by Figure 5e. The observed rise in permeation flux is primarily due to enhancement in driving force. The elevation in operating temperature enhances the driving force across the membrane by increasing the vapour pressure on the feed side, thereby promoting mass transport. This effect significantly improves the overall permeation flux [34]. Along with this, the rise in separation factor at higher temperatures is mainly due to higher sorption of butanol at elevated temperatures. This selective enhancement results in improved separation performance. Similar trends have been reported in previous studies [35,36].

Figure 5f presents the variation of permeate flux with temperature, demonstrating a typical Arrhenius-type dependence commonly observed in pervaporation processes [37]. This relationship is described by the Arrhenius equation:

$$J = J_0 \exp\left(\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (5)$$

where J is the permeate flux, J_0 is the pre-exponential factor (permeation rate constant), R is the universal gas constant, T is the absolute temperature in Kelvin, and E_a represents the apparent activation energy. The value of E_a can be determined by the slope of the linear plot of $\ln(J)$ versus $1/T$. A higher apparent activation energy indicates a stronger temperature dependence of permeate flux, which is a characteristic often reported in pervaporation studies [38]. When E_a is larger for a specific component, its permeation through the membrane becomes more sensitive to temperature variations [39]. As shown in Figure 5f, butanol exhibits a higher activation energy than water, suggesting that its flux is more responsive to increases in temperature. This behaviour implies that at elevated temperatures, butanol permeation is significantly enhanced, potentially improving membrane selectivity towards butanol.

4. Conclusion

In this work, PEBA-PEMA blend membranes as well as ZSM-5 zeolite-added mixed matrix blend membranes were developed and implemented for pervaporation separation of butanol. It shows simple blending and zeolite addition significantly improves butanol separation capability of PEBA polymer. However, polymer blend compatibility poses restriction on the blending ratio and needs to be addressed. The addition of ZSM-5 zeolite into the PEBA-PEMA blend membranes enhanced the hydrophobicity and pervaporation performance of the membranes, resulting in improved separation of butanol from an aqueous solution. The blend membrane PBPM5-5 containing 5 wt% of ZSM-5 zeolite achieved the best PV separation, yielding a flux of $0.21 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ and a separation factor of 21.3, which is an 80% enhancement in flux and approximately a threefold raise in the separation factor as compared to the pristine PEBA membrane. Increasing the feed operating temperature from 30 to 60°C enhanced both flux and separation factor due to increased driving force. The membrane PBPM5-5 at 60°C had the highest flux ($0.25 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$) and separation factor (24). The computed activation energy values indicated that butanol flux is more temperature sensitive than water. Overall, it can be concluded through blending and zeolite incorporation, butanol separation ability of PEBA membranes can be significantly enhanced.

Author contribution

Praveenkumar Danganavar: Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, **Jayachandra Krishnegowda:** Writing – review and editing, **Santosh K. Choudhari:** Visualization, Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review and editing Funding acquisition, Project administration.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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5. References

- [1] Rom A., Esteve D., Friedl A., Organophilic pervaporation of butanol from an aqueous solution with poms, *Chemical Engineering Transactions* 35 1315–1320, 2013.
- [2] L. Liu, Y. Wang, N. Wang, X. Chen, B. Li, J. Shi, X. Li, Process optimization of acetone-butanol-ethanol fermentation integrated with pervaporation for enhanced butanol production, *Biochemical Engineering Journal* 173, 108070, 2021.
- [3] P. Jiménez-Bonilla, Y. Wang, In situ biobutanol recovery from clostridial fermentations: a critical review, *Critical Reviews in Biotechnology* 38, 469–482, 2018.
- [4] C. Xue, F. Liu, M. Xu, I.-C. Tang, J. Zhao, F. Bai, S.-T. Yang, Butanol production in acetone-butanol-ethanol fermentation with in situ product recovery by adsorption, *Bioresource Technology* 219, 158–168, 2016
- [5] H. Zhu, X. Li, Y. Pan, G. Liu, H. Wu, M. Jiang, W. Jin, Fluorinated PDMS membrane with anti-biofouling property for in-situ biobutanol recovery from fermentation-pervaporation coupled process, *Journal of Membrane Science* 609, 118225, 2020
- [6] A. Oudshoorn, L.A. Van Der Wielen, A.J. Straathof, Assessment of options for selective 1-butanol recovery from aqueous solution, *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research* 48, 7325–7336, 2009.
- [7] A.G. Fadeev, M.M. Meagher, S.S. Kelley, V.V. Volkov, Fouling of poly [-1-(trimethylsilyl)-1-propyne] membranes in pervaporative recovery of butanol from aqueous solutions and ABE fermentation broth, *Journal of Membrane Science* 173, 133–144, 2000.
- [8] E.A. Fouad, X. Feng, Pervaporative separation of n-butanol from dilute aqueous solutions using silicalite-filled poly (dimethyl siloxane) membranes, *Journal of Membrane Science* 339, 120–125, 2009.
- [9] Q. Liu, Y. Li, Q. Li, G. Liu, G. Liu, W. Jin, Mixed-matrix hollow fiber composite membranes comprising of PEBA and MOF for pervaporation separation of ethanol/water mixtures, *Separation and Purification Technology* 214, 2–10, 2019
- [10] P. Shao, R.Y.M. Huang, Polymeric membrane pervaporation, *Journal of Membrane Science* 287, 162–179, 2007.
- [11] W.F. Yong, H. Zhang, Recent advances in polymer blend membranes for gas separation and pervaporation, *Progress in Materials Science* 116, 100713, 2021.
- [12] A. Komal, A. Kasuri, M. Yasin, A.L. Khan, A. Razzaq, H. Alhmohamadi, F.H. Akhtar, A.A. Raja, R. Nawaz, E. Abdulmalek, M.A. Gilani, Enhancing butanol separation efficiency in pervaporation with ZIF-8 porous liquid infused mixed matrix membranes, *Chemical Engineering Research and Design* 206, 43–53, 2024.
- [13] K. Liu, Z. Tong, L. Liu, X. Feng, Separation of organic compounds from water by pervaporation in the production of n-butyl acetate via esterification by reactive distillation, *Journal of Membrane Science* 256, 193–201, 2005.
- [14] E.A. Fouad, X. Feng, Use of pervaporation to separate butanol from dilute aqueous solutions: Effects of operating conditions and concentration polarization, *Journal of Membrane Science* 323, 428–435, 2008.
- [15] F. Liu, L. Liu, X. Feng, Separation of acetone-butanol-ethanol (ABE) from dilute aqueous solutions by pervaporation, *Separation and Purification Technology* 42, 273–282, 2005.
- [16] J. Gu, X. Shi, Y. Bai, H. Zhang, L. Zhang, H. Huang, Silicalite-Filled PEBA Membranes for Recovering Ethanol from Aqueous Solution by Pervaporation, *Chemical Engineering & Technology* 32, 155–160, 2009.
- [17] F. Cerrone, S.K. Choudhari, R. Davis, D. Cysneiros, V. O'Flaherty, G. Duane, E. Casey, M.W. Guzik, S.T. Kenny, R.P. Babu, K. O'Connor, Medium chain length polyhydroxyalkanoate (mcl-PHA) production from volatile fatty acids derived from the anaerobic digestion of grass, *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 98, 611–620, 2014.
- [18] K.W. Böddeker, G. Bengtson, H. Pingel, Pervaporation of isomeric butanols, *Journal of Membrane Science* 54, 1–12, 1990.
- [19] H.-W. Yen, Z.-H. Chen, I.-K. Yang, Use of the composite membrane of poly(ether-block-amide) and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in a pervaporation system incorporated with fermentation for butanol production by *Clostridium acetobutylicum*, *Bioresource Technology* 109, 105–109, 2012.
- [20] M.K. Buckley-Smith, The Use of Solubility Parameters to Select Membrane Materials for Pervaporation of Organic Mixtures, (n.d.).
- [21] S. Mandal, V.G. Pangarkar, Effect of membrane morphology in pervaporative separation of isopropyl alcohol-aromatic mixtures— a thermodynamic approach to membrane selection, *J of Applied Polymer Sci* 90, 3912–3921, 2003.
- [22] S.M. Pal, V.G. Pangarkar, Acrylonitrile-based copolymer membranes for the separation of methanol from a methanol-toluene mixture through pervaporation, *J of Applied Polymer Sci* 96, 243–252, 2005.

- [23] Y.-C. Wang, C.-L. Li, J. Huang, C. Lin, K.-R. Lee, D.-J. Liaw, J.-Y. Lai, Pervaporation of benzene/cyclohexane mixtures through aromatic polyamide membranes, *Journal of Membrane Science* 185, 193–200, 2001.
- [24] Y. Zhang, A. Hirata, Y. Nakasaka, T. Tago, T. Taniguchi, T. Masuda, Effects of crystal morphology, Si/Al ratio and thickness of an MTW zeolite membrane on water/2-propanol separation by pervaporation, *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials* 222, 178–184, 2016.
- [25] K. Sato, K. Sugimoto, T. Nakane, Separation of ethanol/ethyl acetate mixture by pervaporation at 100–130°C through NaY zeolite membrane for industrial purpose, *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials* 115, 170–175, 2008.
- [26] H. Tan, Y. Wu, T. Li, Pervaporation of *n*-butanol aqueous solution through ZSM-5-PEBA composite membranes, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* 129, 105–112, 2013.
- [27] J.J. Rosenthal, I.-M. Hsieh, M.M. Malmali, ZSM-5/Thermoplastic Polyurethane Mixed Matrix Membranes for Pervaporation of Binary and Ternary Mixtures of *n*-Butanol, Ethanol, and Water, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 61, 12764–12775, 2022.
- [28] M. Vatani, A. Raisi, G. Pazuki, Mixed matrix membrane of ZSM-5/poly (ether-block-amide)/polyethersulfone for pervaporation separation of ethyl acetate from aqueous solution, *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials* 263, 257–267, 2018.
- [29] Y. Ban, L. Jin, Y. Li, H. Yang, H. Hu, Pyrolysis behaviors of model compounds with representative oxygen-containing functional groups in carbonaceous feedstock over calcium, *Fuel* 335, 127137, 2023.
- [30] A. Ortega, H.I. Meléndez-Ortiz, L. García-Uriostegui, G. Ávila-Soria, Drug delivery system based on poly(ether-block-amide) and acrylic acid for controlled release of vancomycin, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 135, 45745, 2018.
- [31] M. Asghari, M. Mosadegh, H. Riasat Harami, Supported PEBA-zeolite 13X nano-composite membranes for gas separation: Preparation, characterization and molecular dynamics simulation, *Chemical Engineering Science* 187, 67–78, 2018.
- [32] Z. Huang, X. Ru, Y.-T. Zhu, Y. Guo, L. Teng, Poly(vinyl alcohol)/ZSM-5 zeolite mixed matrix membranes for pervaporation dehydration of isopropanol/water solution through response surface methodology, *Chemical Engineering Research and Design* 144, 19–34, 2019.
- [33] C. Arregoitia-Sarabia, D. González-Revuelta, M. Fallanza, D. Gorri, I. Ortiz, Polymer inclusion membranes containing ionic liquids for the recovery of *n*-butanol from ABE solutions by pervaporation, *Separation and Purification Technology* 248, 117101, 2020.
- [34] H. Sanaeepur, S. Mashhadikhan, G. Mardassi, A. Ebadi Amooghin, B. Van der Bruggen, A. Moghadassi, Aminosilane cross-linked poly ether-block-amide PEBAX 2533: Characterization and CO₂ separation properties, *Korean J. Chem. Eng.* 36 (2019) 1339–1349. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11814-019-0323-x>.
- [35] L.T.P. Trinh, Y.J. Lee, H.-J. Bae, H.-J. Lee, Pervaporative separation of butanol using a composite PDMS/PEI hollow fiber membrane, *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry* 20 (2014) 2814–2818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiec.2013.11.012>.
- [36] A. Khan, M. Ali, A. Ilyas, P. Naik, I.F.J. Vankelecom, M.A. Gilani, M.R. Bilad, Z. Sajjad, A.L. Khan, ZIF-67 filled PDMS mixed matrix membranes for recovery of ethanol via pervaporation, *Separation and Purification Technology* 206 (2018) 50–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2018.05.055>.
- [37] L. Aouinti, M. Belbachir, A maghnite-clay-H/ polymer membrane for separation of ethanol–water azeotrope, *Applied Clay Science* 39 (2008) 78–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2007.04.014>.
- [38] V. García, E. Pongrácz, E. Muurinen, R.L. Keiski, Pervaporation of dichloromethane from multicomponent aqueous systems containing *n*-butanol and sodium chloride, *Journal of Membrane Science* 326 (2009) 92–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2008.09.027>.
- [39] A.B. Beltran, G.M. Nisola, E.L. Vivas, W. Cho, W.-J. Chung, Poly(octylmethylsiloxane)/oleyl alcohol supported liquid membrane for the pervaporative recovery of 1-butanol from aqueous and ABE model solutions, *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry* 19 (2013) 182–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiec.2012.07.022>.